

OVRO-LWA Stage 2 Performance

Versions

1. Initial skeleton (CJL, 19 February 2020)
2. Filling in analysis types (all, 4 March 2020)
3. Adding detail (all, 18 March 2020)
4. Flagging, calibration (CJL, 28 March 2020)
5. Review with Gregg (CJL, 7 April 2020)
6. Adding deep Stokes V and conclusions (CJL, 2 June 2020)
7. Feedback in prep for new cluster (CJL, 11 August 2020)

Introduction

With the end of data collection for stage 2, it is a good time to review performance of the array. The goal of this memo is to capture the current performance of the array, particularly in terms of imaging sensitivity and computing time. Characterizing the performance of stage 2 will help us predict stage 3 performance and the software development required to meet our science goals.

The phase 2 correlator and data analysis software are shown here (courtesy M. Anderson):

This memo is broken into sections that summarize the theoretical expectations for image sensitivity, along with actual sensitivity in a range of applications. We also describe the computational time for the current standard calibration and imaging pipeline. The memo closes with conclusions on the nature of the current limitations and developments required for the stage 3 array.

Theoretical Expectations (Casey)

Phase 2 OVRO-LWA:

- 1.5 km baselines, 288 antennas, 30-80 MHz
- Beam size 9' to 23'
- SEFD~3900 for 256 ants (SEFD/ant ~ 1e6 Jy; Eastwood+)
- Snapshot sensitivity (13 s, 50 MHz band, Stokes I) ~ 150 mJy/beam
- M-mode sensitivity (24h, 50 MHz band, Stokes I) ~ 4mJy/beam
- Confusion limit (60 MHz, Stokes I) ~ 800 mJy/beam
- Confusion limit (60 MHz, Stokes V, 3% leakage) ~ 24 mJy

Phase 3 OVRO-LWA:

- 2.6 km baselines, 352 antennas, 30-80 MHz
- Beam size 5' to 13'
- SEFD~3500 for 352 ants (SEFD/ant ~ 1e6 Jy; Eastwood+)
- Snapshot sensitivity (13 s, 50 MHz, Stokes I) ~ 140 mJy/beam
- M-mode sensitivity (24h, 50 MHz, Stokes I) ~ 1.7 mJy/beam
- Classical confusion limit (60 MHz, Stokes I) ~ 300 mJy/beam (Assuming 900 mJy/beam confusion in Stage 2)
- Classical confusion limit (60 MHz, Stokes V, 3% leakage) ~ 9 mJy

Classical confusion limit

- $\sigma_c = 30e-6 (\theta/1'')^{1.54} (\nu/74\text{MHz})^{-0.7}$ (Cohen LWA memo, van Haarlem et al 2013)
- Note that the VLSSr (Cohen LWA memo) probably overstates confusion at flux densities below 1 Jy (e.g., see MWA analysis in Franzen et al 2012).
- M. Eastwood (mmode; unpublished): noise floor 430 mJy (1 MHz band at 74 MHz) implies 400 mJy confusion+common-mode noise. Upper limit on classical confusion limit.
- Anderson et al 2018: Phase 2 confusion limit ~800 mJy in 13 s for whole band.

Sidelobe confusion limit

- Best to estimate by using synthesized beam, sky model, and calibration errors in forward model
- Or take far sidelobes as $1/N$ in a snapshot confusion for a given flux density distribution.

Flagging, Calibration, and Data Quality

Stationary noise

- Extra noise of unidentified origin is known to have both time and frequency dependence. Seems to improve after installation of ferrites to filter signal.
- Anderson et al (2019): near-field source is peeled with TTCal to remove stationary noise pattern. Stokes V image with/without full-stokes near-field peeling has noise floor of 330/590 mJy/beam (no ferrites). That implies near-field peeled "source" is a 500 mJy/beam noise term.

Flagging

- Anderson et al (2019):
 - All flagging implemented in custom Python (part of calim code).

- Flagged 50/256 bad antennas, 2% of baselines for cross-coupling, 240/2398 channels for a total of 40% of all recorded visibilities. Flagging done per integration (no time-based flags).
- Most antennas and baseline flagging done by knowledge of array design. Others are based on data.
- During calibration, CASA flags some baselines with no solution.
- After calibration, bad data was identified manually and flagged as with raw data.
- Eastwood et al (2019):
 - All flagging implemented in custom Julia code (part of mmode code).
 - Acts on raw data and on the calibrated data. The algorithm processes 3 channel differenced timestreams in a few ways:
 - Looking for spiky events in the autocorrelations
 - Comparing the time-averaged amplitude of either the autos or the visibilities to the RMS.
 - The smoothing of the sawtooth from the HVAC is also applied here.
 - 400 GB disk space per day/subband for raw and transposed data.

Calibration

- Anderson et al (2019):
 - Implemented with CASA `bandpass` and `TTCal` peeling.
 - 2-src sky model with complex gain per ant/channel. One solution based on 13s of data per day.
- Eastwood et al (2019):
 - Implemented in Julia as `TTCal`
 - Uses the iterative least squares scheme and a sky model consisting of CygA and CasA.

Snapshot All-Sky (Marin)

Analysis: "Standard pipeline" output: single (13 s) integration, full BW (26-84 MHz) image with Cas A and Cyg A peeled. `WSClean` with `4096x4096` images with `robust=0`.

Performance:

- Stokes I ~ 800 mJy noise (with deconvolution, niter=50,000)
- Stokes V ~ 500 mJy noise. Noise floor integrates down to ~ 100 mJy.
- Typical $N_{\text{sources}}(>4.5\sigma) = 1500$

Limitations:

- Classical confusion in Stokes I
- Stokes V: Stokes I leakage, common-mode noise

Deep Stokes V (Gregg)

Analysis: Similar to pipeline analysis, but integrating in time and over “exoplanet band” (33 – 48 MHz). The 1000-hr exoplanet data set was recorded with a range of ferrite setups, but later times have aggressive ferrite setup that improve data quality.

Performance:

- Stokes V ~ 30 mJy image noise in xx hours and yy MHz bandwidth.

Limitations:

- Stokes V confusion limited by Stokes I confusion signal and leakage ($\sim 3\%$). Likely also some common-mode noise.

M-Mode (Phil)

Analysis: The *m*-mode pipeline can be divided into several major analysis steps: collect up a day of data, Fourier transform along its time axis to *m*-modes, compute Tikhonov-regularized maps (/alms), foreground filter, compute power spectra.

Performance:

- Eastwood et al (2019) reports ~ 800 mJy/beam noise in eight 24-kHz bands from 30-80 MHz in 28 hours.
- *m*-mode map making needs a few TB disk space overhead for beam transfer matrices

Limitation:

- Sky model is simple, which may introduce errors.
- Operates on a full day of data (large disk space overhead)
- Currently only operates on XX and YY \rightarrow Stokes I
- Sensitivity is similar to confusion limit in Stokes I

Single-Channel Image Noise (Kathryn)

Analysis:

Add channel differencing SEFD measurements from telecon (maybe on slack?)

Performance:

Limitation:

Sidereal Subtraction (Yuping)

Analysis: Since the array is, first and foremost, confusion limited, image differencing is needed to look for transients. Subsequent frame subtractions work less well for images separated by longer than a few integrations because sources have moved considerably across the primary beam. Sidereal subtraction, in theory, allows us to look more transients with up to 1 day timescale with the same sensitivity as 13-s timescale subsequent frame subtraction, since sources roughly remain in the same positions of the primary beam. Sidereal subtraction takes two integrations (with a priori flags applied) that are one sidereal day apart and does the following

- Apply the bandpass solution from the same time
- Peel
- Flag channels for each integration
- Merge the flags
- Image each integration
- Apply analog gain variation correction
- Hogbom remove the Crab and the Sun from the images if present
- Subtract the two images
- Optional: average the subtracted images in time.

Performance: Sidereal subtraction currently achieves about ~20% higher rms than does 13-s subsequent frame subtraction (~900mJy rms at zenith). Averaging in time gives ~200mJy for 20 minutes. The processing time is dominated by peeling. The source count is dominated by refracted sources.

Limitation: Handling the variable things: source refraction, the moving Sun, variable strong sources, long-term gain variation, completely de-correlated stationary noise pattern. Scalability to 137 hours.

Computing Time

Current cluster: 10 nodes, 2x8 cores with 62x10 GB RAM total.

Snap shot imaging single-node performance times:

- Flagging, calibrating, unpolarized peeling of data set on single integration, all subbands: 96 min. (CASA-based “zesting” performs similarly)
- Non-deconvolved image, single integration, all subbands: 4 min.
- Deconvolved image, single integration, all subbands: 72 min.
- Flagging, calibration, and peeling parallelize over subband and integration, while imaging parallelizes over integration only.
- End-to-end processing to images is 8.5x real time on current cluster (10 nodes with *6* processes per node). Not clear if this is I/O or CPU bound yet.

M-mode imaging:

- Flagging takes 2 hours to compute flags per day/subband and 2 hours to apply.
- Calibration takes 1 hour of 1 core per node on 9 nodes
- M-mode imaging takes 1 hour of 1 core per node on 9 nodes ($l_{\max} = 300$)
- Peeling (CygA, CasA, and Sun, subtract 5 other sources) takes 13 hours on 6 cores per node.

Other data products and computing:

- Cosmic Ray classification will be done on site (other computing will be done elsewhere)
- Most beamformed data will be taken away
- Need to develop a plan for on-demand computing

Limitations

Well-characterized limitations:

- Classical confusion: 800 mJy/beam (snapshot) or < 400 mJy/beam (mmode)

- Common-mode noise (~ 500 mJy/beam noise floor before ferrite installation)
- Polarization calibration (3% in idealized beam model, 10% near horizon; M. Anderson thesis)

Likely limitations:

- Sidelobe confusion
- Incomplete sky model
- Scintillating sources
- Artifacts introduced by using single beam model for all antennas
- Computing limit from peeling on every integration. Data preparation/correction could reduce compute demand (e.g., remove A/C cycle)

Conclusions

Performance in Stage 2 is largely limited by confusion and common-mode noise. The science analysis software is driven by these limitations in that, for example by using Stokes V or difference imaging to circumvent the confusion limit. These strategies work in Stage 2 and are expected to work in Stage 3, but rely on good data quality and lots of computing power.

The 1000-hour (“exoplanet”) data set recorded in late Stage 2 will be a valuable for science and as a demonstration of how to run real-time processing in Stage 3. This data set was designed to avoid the common-mode noise issue and has relatively low RFI. It was recorded mostly in a contiguous segment, which facilitates mmode imaging. The OVRO-LWA team will work to process this data set with a uniform pipeline and coherent set of output data products.

Science analysis in the Stage 3 array will be supported by a dedicated “Callm” cluster. As described in this memo, the Stage 2 algorithms can be applied to processing in the Stage 3 array to achieve the nominal science plan.

The baseline design is for a 24 node cluster with 2x20 cores and 192x24 GB RAM per node. This definition is preliminary and largely driven by the experience of the Stage 2 array. If the time is bound in a similar way (either compute or I/O at various parts of pipeline), then the processing power will be 4x faster (24 nodes x 10 processes per node / 10 nodes x 6 processes per node = 4x), but potentially 2x further improvement from using all cores (no I/O bound). The data rate will be 2*(13/10) higher (combining visibility rate and sampling time change). This is sufficient to produce standard data products (peeled visibilities and snapshot images) at a rate of 5.5x real-time.